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THE IMPACT OF THE APPLICATION OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN MATHEMATICS TEACHING ON STUDENT ACHIEVEMENTS

KHATIRA SARBAZ GIZI MAGSUDOVA

Mathematics teacher
at “Young Talents” Lyceum
under Baku State University

Summary. *The rapid development of digital technologies in the modern education system has had a significant impact on the content, methods and results of the learning process. The application of digital technologies in mathematics teaching is of particular importance in terms of improving students' academic achievements, developing logical thinking and increasing their motivation to learn. The article examines the theoretical foundations of the application of digital technologies in mathematics teaching, analyzes the results of international research and assesses their impact on student achievement. The study shows that interactive software, artificial intelligence-based platforms, gamified learning systems and virtual learning environments facilitate the acquisition of mathematical concepts, develop problem-solving skills and increase the quality of learning. At the same time, the effectiveness of technologies depends on their integration with pedagogical goals and the digital competence of teachers. The analysis shows that information and communication technologies, electronic educational resources, interactive programs and digital platforms have a significant impact on improving the quality of teaching in mathematics, increasing students' cognitive activity and improving their academic results. In the works of Eastern and Russian researchers, it is emphasized that digital technologies facilitate the visualization of abstract mathematical concepts, create personalized learning opportunities and contribute to the development of students' logical thinking. It is also noted that the effective application of digital tools depends on the professional and digital competencies of the teacher.*

Keywords: *digital technologies, mathematics education, student achievement, artificial intelligence, innovative education, digital pedagogy, digital technologies, information and communication technologies, digital educational environment, interactive learning, electronic educational resources, academic indicators.*

RƏQƏMSAL TEXNOLOGİYALARIN RİYAZİYYAT TƏLİMİNDƏ TƏTBİQİNİN ŞAĞİRD NAILİYYƏTLƏRİNƏ TƏSİRİ

XATIRƏ SARBAZ QIZI MAQSUDOVA

Bakı Dövlət Universitetinin nəzdində
“Gənc İstedadlar” liseyinin riyaziyyat müəllimi

Xülasə. *Müasir təhsil sistemində rəqəmsal texnologiyaların sürətli inkişafı təlim prosesinin məzmununa, metodlarına və nəticələrinə mühüm təsir göstərmişdir. Riyaziyyatın tədrisində rəqəmsal texnologiyaların tətbiqi şagirdlərin akademik nailiyyətlərinin yüksəldilməsi, məntiqi təfəkkürünün inkişaf etdirilməsi və öyrənməyə motivasiyasının artırılması baxımından xüsusi əhəmiyyət daşıyır. Məqalədə rəqəmsal texnologiyaların riyaziyyat təlimində tətbiqinin nəzəri əsasları araşdırılmış, beynəlxalq tədqiqatların nəticələri təhlil edilmiş və onların şagird nailiyyətlərinə təsiri qiymətləndirilmişdir. Tədqiqat göstərir ki, interaktiv proqram təminatı, süni intellekt əsaslı platformalar, oyunlaşdırılmış təlim sistemləri və virtual öyrənmə mühitləri riyazi anlayışların mənimsənilməsini asanlaşdırır, problem həll etmə bacarıqlarını inkişaf etdirir və öyrənmənin keyfiyyətini artırır. Bununla yanaşı, texnologiyaların effektivliyi onların pedaqoji məqsədlərlə inteqrasiyası və müəllimlərin rəqəmsal sərəfşəllərindən asılıdır. Təhlil göstərir ki, informasiya-kommunikasiya texnologiyaları, elektron təhsil resursları, interaktiv proqramlar və rəqəmsal*

platformalar riyaziyyatın tədrisində təlimin keyfiyyətinin yüksəldilməsinə, şagirdlərin idrak fəallığının artırılmasına və akademik nəticələrinin yaxşılaşmasına mühüm təsir göstərir. Şərq və rus tədqiqatçılarının əsərlərində rəqəmsal texnologiyaların abstrakt riyazi anlayışların vizuallaşdırılmasını asanlaşdırdığı, fərdiləşdirilmiş təlim imkanları yaratdığı və şagirdlərin məntiqi təfəkkürünün inkişafına şərait yaratdığı vurğulanır. Həmçinin qeyd olunur ki, rəqəmsal vasitələrin effektiv tətbiqi müəllimin peşəkar və rəqəmsal kompetensiyalarından asılıdır.

***Açar sözlər:** rəqəmsal texnologiyalar, riyaziyyat təlimi, şagird nailiyyətləri, süni intellekt, innovativ təhsil, rəqəmsal pedaqogika, rəqəmsal texnologiyalar, informasiya-kommunikasiya texnologiyaları, rəqəmsal təhsil mühiti, interaktiv təlim, elektron təhsil resursları, akademik göstəricilər.*

Introduction

One of the main features of the 21st century education system is the digitalization of the learning process. The development of information and communication technologies has led to the transformation of traditional teaching models and has led to the emergence of new approaches in the educational process. Especially in the field of mathematics teaching, digital technologies have created wide opportunities for the visualization of abstract concepts, modeling of complex calculations and involving students in the active learning process (Cheung, Slavin, 2013). In modern educational research, mathematical literacy is assessed not only as the ability to perform calculations, but also as the ability to analyze problems, draw logical conclusions and apply mathematical knowledge in real-life situations. In this regard, digital technologies have become an important tool in the formation of students' mathematical competencies (OECD, 2023). The results of international assessments show that students' mathematical achievements are higher in schools that use technology effectively (OECD, 2023). However, some studies emphasize that integrating technology into teaching does not always yield high results and that it must be applied in accordance with pedagogical goals (Rakes et al., 2020).

Modern studies conducted in Eastern countries show that digital technologies play an important role in improving the quality of mathematics education. Studies conducted in Arab countries confirm that technology has a positive impact on students' academic achievement, motivation and the formation of mathematical thinking. For example, a study conducted in the Sultanate of Oman showed a statistically significant relationship between a positive attitude towards e-learning and academic achievement in mathematics (Al-Kamashki, Yusuf, 2024). A large-scale study conducted in Arab countries based on TIMSS-2019 data proved that students' mathematics performance is higher in schools that use modern teaching strategies and technology-supported methods. The study showed that the level of teachers' use of innovative methods is one of the main predictors of student achievement (AlSalouli et al., 2024). A study conducted in Qatar found that the application of gamified digital systems in Arabic-language mathematics education increased both students' motivation and academic results. Researchers note that digital game elements help to overcome psychological barriers to mathematics (Moreno, Bahameish, Al-Thani, 2025).

Studies conducted in Jordan have shown that the use of Augmented Reality technologies in mathematics education has a positive effect on the development of students' spatial thinking and ability to grasp geometric concepts. These technologies facilitate the visualization of complex mathematical objects and make learning more interactive (Abutayeh, Kraishan, Kraishan, 2022). A meta-analytic study conducted by Turkish researcher Zehra Taşpınar Şener found that mathematics education organized through technology has an above-average effect. The author emphasizes that technology-supported learning environments have a significant impact on mathematical achievements (Şener, 2023). Kazakh scientists Kerimbayev and Akramova, investigating the integration of ethnomathematics and digital education approaches noted that the use of national-cultural components in mathematics education increases students' interest. In their opinion ethnocultural mathematical materials presented in a digital environment serve to develop both the mathematical and cultural identity of students.

Also in the Russian-language pedagogical and methodological literature, the integration of digital technologies into mathematics teaching is considered an important direction in terms of improving the quality of teaching, increasing students' cognitive activity and improving their academic achievements. According to researchers, digital educational resources facilitate the visualization of abstract mathematical concepts, stimulate students' independent activity and create personalized learning opportunities (Полат, 2017; Роберт, 2014). Among Russian scientists, Polat emphasizes that the use of digital technologies in the teaching process increases the interactivity of teaching and develops students' problem-solving skills. According to the author, electronic educational resources have a positive effect on students' motivation to learn and create conditions for improving their learning outcomes (Полат, 2017). I. B. Robert, analyzing the application of information and communication technologies (ICT) to the education system, shows that computer modeling and the use of interactive programs contribute to a deeper assimilation of mathematical concepts. Dynamic software, especially in teaching geometry and functions, has a significant impact on the development of students' logical thinking (Robert, 2014). Russian methodologists M.P. Lapchik, E.K. Henner, and A.A. Kuznechev, studying the application of the digital environment in teaching, note that electronic learning tools increase the speed of students' mastering of educational material and allow for the formation of individual learning trajectories. Their studies have shown that academic performance in classes where digital technologies are used is higher than that of students receiving traditional training (Lapchik et al., 2021). Experimental studies conducted in Russia have shown that the level of mathematical literacy of students increases as a result of the use of GeoGebra, electronic testing systems, and virtual learning platforms. These technologies provide a visual presentation of complex concepts, allowing students to immediately see and correct their mistakes, which increases the effectiveness of training (Bosova, 2020). Another Russian researcher L.L. Basova, analyzing the formation of a digital educational environment, emphasizes that the systematic use of electronic resources creates conditions for the development of information culture, algorithmic thinking, and analytical skills in students. These characteristics are considered one of the important factors in achieving high achievements in mathematics (Босова, 2020). Russian-language sources also note that the effective use of digital technologies directly depends on the teacher's digital competence. As the teacher's level of technological preparation increases, the integration of digital tools into teaching becomes more purposeful and result-oriented (Роберт, 2014; Полат, 2017). Thus, the analysis of Russian-language sources suggests that the use of digital technologies in mathematics teaching increases students' learning motivation, facilitates the assimilation of abstract concepts, develops logical and critical thinking, creates personalized learning opportunities and has a positive effect on increasing academic achievements.

The purpose of this article is to investigate the impact of the application of digital technologies in mathematics teaching on student achievement from theoretical and empirical aspects.

Problem statement

Mathematics is considered one of the most complex and abstract subjects in school education. Many students face difficulties in mastering mathematical concepts, which negatively affects their academic performance. In modern times, the effectiveness of digital technologies in solving these problems is one of the pressing issues of pedagogy. The main question of the study was defined as follows: How does the application of digital technologies in mathematics teaching affect students' academic achievement?

Research methodology

The study is based on the method of systematic literature review. During the analysis, scientific sources covering the years 2015–2025 indexed in the Web of Science, Scopus, ERIC and Google Scholar databases were studied. The methodological basis of the study is comparative analysis, systematic literature review, generalization of meta-analytic results, interpretation of statistical data, etc.

According to the constructivist learning theory, knowledge is actively constructed by the learner (Piaget, 1972). Digital technologies create the opportunity for students to conduct experiments,

formulate hypotheses and evaluate the results in this process. Vygotsky's social-constructivist theory emphasizes that learning is carried out through social interactions (Vygotsky, 1978). Modern digital platforms create conditions for the practical application of this theory by creating collaborative learning environments. Papert (1980) considered computer technologies to be one of the main tools of the constructivist learning model. In his opinion, technologies allow students to learn abstract mathematical concepts through concrete models.

Interactive mathematics programs GeoGebra, Desmos, and Wolfram Alpha provide a wide range of opportunities for graphing functions, creating geometric constructions, and processing statistical data. According to a meta-analysis by Sofroniou et al. (2025), visualization technologies have the highest impact on the acquisition of mathematical concepts. Artificial intelligence-based systems allow for the creation of adaptive learning environments. Such systems identify the individual needs of students and provide them with appropriate tasks. Luckin and Holmes (2017) note that artificial intelligence-based learning platforms significantly increase the effectiveness of personalized learning. Gamified learning The integration of game elements into the learning process increases student motivation. Byun and Joung's (2018) meta-analysis showed that game-based learning has a positive effect on increasing interest in mathematics. Virtual and augmented reality Virtual reality environments allow for the presentation of complex geometric models in three-dimensional form. These technologies are considered especially effective in the development of spatial thinking.

Meta-analytic studies have shown that technology-assisted instruction has a positive effect on mathematics achievement. Higgins and colleagues (2019) found that the use of technology had a moderate positive effect. Cheung and Slavin (2013) noted that technology-based instructional programs had a statistically significant effect on mathematics achievement. Ran and colleagues (2020) found that computer technology produced higher results among students with low academic performance.

The main directions of the impact on academic achievement are:

1. Increasing mathematical results;
2. Developing problem-solving skills;
3. Strengthening logical thinking;
4. Increasing motivation to learn;
5. Developing independent learning skills.

Discussion

The results obtained show that digital technologies play an important role in improving the quality of mathematics teaching. However, the effectiveness of technology depends not on the intensity of its use, but on its application in accordance with pedagogical goals. OECD reports emphasize that schools that use technology in a balanced way achieve higher results. Excessive use of technology can sometimes lead to a decrease in academic achievement (OECD, 2023). In addition, developing teachers' digital competencies and improving the technical provision of schools are important conditions.

Conclusion

The study shows that digital technologies increase the effectiveness of mathematics teaching, visualization programs facilitate the acquisition of mathematical concepts, artificial intelligence-based systems support personalized learning, gamified platforms increase motivation, and the effectiveness of technology depends on the teacher's professionalism and pedagogical strategies. In future studies, it is considered appropriate to study the impact of artificial intelligence and big data technologies on mathematics teaching on an experimental basis. It confirms that the use of digital technologies in mathematics teaching has a positive effect on students' motivation, independent activity skills and learning achievements.

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